

MODERN APPROACHES TO TEACH WRITING IN A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Introduction. Approaches to teaching writing in a foreign language are closely related to research in the field of discourse since discourse competence is an integral part of communicative competence. It is logical to assume that the understanding of discourse as a result in the form of text and as a cognitive process of creating meaning is interconnected with the terms "product" and "process" in the theory of teaching foreign languages. These two opposing terms have been implemented in approaches to teaching writing known as the modern-rhetorical (product-oriented) and process-based approaches. 405 is Theoretical background. Both approaches have developed since the 60s and 70s. in the 20th century, finding its supporters and opponents. In recent decades, in relation to teaching writing, another term "post-process" has appeared, which understood as a reflection of the social context in the discursive construction of reality in the writing process (Trimbur, Atkinson) [4]. This approach to writing attempts to synthesize and overcome the shortcomings of previous approaches, but it is primarily a continuation of the process approach. The post-processual approach, according to its supporters, opens new opportunities in understanding writing as a multicomponent activity in teaching writing in a foreign language. The modern rhetorical approach to teaching writing took shape in a coherent theory earlier than the procedural approach. Even though the term "procedural" is often found in the methodological literature on the problem of teaching writing in a foreign language and is the subject of many foreign studies, the procedural approach is still not a coherent methodological theory. In addition, it is fair to note that the distinction between "productive" and "processual" approaches to teaching writing is quite arbitrary, because in practice they use elements of each other. Firstly, this is reflected in the fact that not the entire community of English language teachers is familiar with the ideas of the process approach and shares them. Secondly, most educational and methodological complexes in the English language contain tasks of a mixed type, which involve both writing texts based on samples and creative work. as The modern rhetorical approach to teaching foreign language writing served a steppingstone for the beginning of research in the field of writing as a process. The term was coined by D Fogarty and R Young in the 70s to describe the traditional ways that were used to develop writing and rhetorical skills. In other words, the term described research into writing instruction that focused more on the outcome than the process of writing. The emphasis in teaching written discourse shifted to words, individual sentences and paragraphs connected syntactically, spelling, punctuation and style (Berlin, Crowley) [4]. Methodology. Since the emergence of the term "modern rhetorical," the method of teaching writing has consisted of performing controlled tasks containing instructions on the genre and purpose of the written work, the volume of the statement and the plan for constructing the text (Silva, Connor, Leckie, Grabe and Kaplan) [3]. The most rigorous form of manifestation of this approach in teaching was tasks, usually consisting of five paragraphs, within which students must build sentences in the correct logical sequence and use language forms typical of native

speakers in tasks of the specified genre, that is, fill the template with new meaning. Students are expected to analyze and copy samples, identifying the general theme of the text, the main sentence in each paragraph, and the sentences that detail it. A distinctive feature of the modern rhetorical approach is that the formation of writing skills is practiced not so much at the sentence level as at the paragraph and text level. Within this approach, much attention is paid to the organizational units of the text: introduction, main part and conclusion, as well as genres: description, narration, and argumentation. Teaching techniques include analyzing samples of written discourse, developing main content ideas, and drawing up a plan. However, the topic of the written work is determined by the teacher, not the students, and the final text is not usually reviewed jointly with students. This technique made it possible to classify this approach as a teacher-centered approach. At one time, this teaching method was also called prescriptive and static, which did not allow it to fully realize its potential [3]. In our opinion, the potential of this method is obvious in the early stages of learning to write in a foreign language, because it helps to understand the organization, semantic structure of the text and its linguistic features. Sample tasks of this kind are irreplaceable, because before performing creative tasks with an open answer in a foreign language, the student must understand how this can be done. Teaching with the help of sample tests does not detract from or hinder the development of students' creative abilities. After all, there is still insufficient experimental evidence to support Hyland's thesis that writing is learned, not taught [3]. This is the main disagreement between adherents of results-oriented and process oriented approaches. The traditional approach has been repeatedly criticized for not allowing students to develop individuality and creative writing skills. However, we find confirmation of its prevalence and effectiveness from an assessment point of view in tasks of a similar format in Part C of the Unified State Examination in English. In task C2 the student must write a 5-paragraph essay on a formulated problem. Despite the fact that the task is classified as creative, and the student is required to express his opinion, its scope is quite strict, since each of the paragraphs fulfills a certain point of the plan: reformulate the problem, express your opinion, give 2-3 arguments, present the opposite point of view with 1-2 arguments, give counterarguments, draw conclusion. In addition, compliance with politeness norms characteristic of native English speakers, the use of vocabulary appropriate to the content, and the use linking words within the text are assessed. It is clear that the formulation of the brief contains both elements of a traditional product-oriented approach and some degree of creativity. The modern rhetorical approach became a steppingstone on the path from tasks that were completely controlled by the teacher to so-called "free" or uncontrolled writing. Alternative trends appeared simultaneously with the growing interest of methodologists in the problem of teaching composite on in a foreign language. It was assumed that they would all ow considering the individuality and needs of the writing student, as well as giving him greater freedom in choosing the topic, structure, form and content of the written work. One of the most well-known terms for writing these tendencies has become the "process approach" in teaching writing, reflecting humanistic tendencies (Taylor, Sammel, Krol, Sasser, Tobin, Appleby) [4]. Characteristic teaching methods for the process approach are work in small groups, which promotes closer interaction between students and the teacher, a variety of tasks, revision of assessment criteria, a mandatory preliminary stage of writing a draft and its analysis. These techniques are also typical for modern teaching aids in the English language. However, the term "procedural" does not at all mean a rejection of traditional tasks of

substitution, transformation, construction of sentences and paragraphs. Changing the approach to teaching writing to a procedural one did not mean an abandonment of traditional methods of teaching rhetoric, but its proponents advocated that 407 students be able to make purposeful choices when completing written tasks and reflect their social, cultural and personal experiences in them (Arapof, Lawrence) [4]. In other words, writing in teaching a foreign language should not only be a completed and assessed task, but should fulfill a communicative task that is significant for the learner.

In conclusion, speaking about the feasibility of a mixed approach to teaching writing in a foreign language, we believe that the procedural component should be realized in the development of discursive meaning during the interaction between the student and the teacher.

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